

Using bench protocol platforms to improve compliance with systematic review guidance documents and reporting checklists: proof of concept

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Abstract

Context: A significant number of guidance documents and reporting checklists have been published to support researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews (SRs). However, compliance of researchers with SR guidance and reporting checklists remains a significant challenge, with the majority of published SRs lacking in one or more aspects of rigour of methods and transparency of reporting.

Objective: To explore how bench protocol development platforms might be repurposed for improving compliance of SRs with conduct guidance and reporting checklists.

System design: We developed a proof-of-concept technology stack based around a general-purpose, guidance- and checklist-compliant SR protocol that was built in protocols.io. We used the protocols.io platform to create an integrated research planning and data collection process for planning guidance-compliant SRs. We used our own custom code and the mustache templating language to automatically create checklist-compliant first-draft SR protocol documents in Microsoft Word

Discussion: Creating the operational process for SR protocol planning and the technology stack for automated documentation allowed us to develop our theoretical understanding of how such a system may

27 improve compliance with research conduct and reporting standards. This includes the potential value of
28 algorithmic rather than heuristic approaches to conducting and reporting research studies, positioning of
29 labelled data rather than a study manuscript as the primary product of the research process, and viewing
30 the process of developing research standards as being analogous to development of open software. Our
31 study also allowed us to identify a number of technological issues that will need to be addressed to
32 enable further development and testing of our proposed approach. These include limitations in templating
33 language, especially when working in Microsoft Word, and the need for more data labelling and export
34 formats from protocols.io.

35

36 Introduction

37 A number of conduct guidelines and reporting checklists have been published to support
38 researchers in planning, doing, and writing up scientifically rigorous systematic reviews (SRs).
39 However, compliance with SR conduct guidelines and reporting checklists appears to be a
40 significant challenge for researchers, with consistent evidence of shortcomings in the
41 methodological rigour and comprehensiveness of documentation of SRs from a range of
42 research fields including healthcare (Page *et al.*, 2016; Gao *et al.*, 2019), environmental science
43 (Pullin *et al.*, 2022), socioeconomics (Wang *et al.*, 2021), and human environmental health
44 (Menon, Struijs and Whaley, 2022). This is potentially a significant source of research waste or
45 even societal harm, with significant resources being used to conduct SRs that may be
46 redundant, present inaccurate findings, or both (Ioannidis, 2016).

47 Conduct guidelines specify what a SR ought to do, in order to attain a certain level of
48 scientific quality, with “quality” generally understood as some desired combination of usefulness,
49 credibility (e.g. by reducing bias), and transparency (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). SR
50 guidelines tend to be lengthy and complex. The Institute of Medicine guidance on SRs consists
51 of 82 performance elements and extensive narrative text (Institute of Medicine, 2011). The
52 Cochrane MECIR standard consists of over 75 performance elements accompanied by a
53 handbook of over 700 pages (Cochrane, 2019; Higgins, JPT *et al.*, 2019). The COSTER
54 recommendations for SRs of environmental health research of consists of 70 elements (Whaley,
55 Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020). Length and complexity of guidance is probably unavoidable when
56 formalising the necessary components of a research process that is in itself lengthy and
57 complex. Nonetheless, such complexity presents a considerable organisational challenge for
58 authors seeking to comply with a SR guideline. This challenge requires a significant level of
59 experience to overcome, to understand specialist vocabulary used in guidance documents and
60 the often complex concepts that terms in the vocabulary may signify, and the unmentioned
61 actions and practices (relating to e.g. resourcing, management, training, and documentation)
62 that need to be undertaken to comply with an superficially simple recommendation or
63 requirement. Nuance and cultural knowledge of this type is challenging, if not impossible, for a
64 guidance document of finite length to provide, or at least for a user of guidance to successfully
65 internalise.

66 Reporting checklists are intended to support authors in providing enough information about
67 what they did and found in the course of conducting a SR that a reader can follow their methods
68 and appraise the credibility of their results (Moher *et al.*, 2014). As for conduct guidelines, we

69 believe there is a high experience requirement for their successful use. One aspect of this
70 experience requirement is the necessity for users and writers of a checklist to share the same
71 understanding of how terms describing checklist items map onto the processes of a systematic
72 review. Ways in which we have observed this breaking down in a PRISMA report (Page *et al.*,
73 2021), for example, include the misidentification of risk of bias with other study appraisal
74 methods, and the conflation of the Population-Exposure-Comparator-Outcome (PECO)
75 statement for describing the objectives of a SR with PECO-derived eligibility criteria for a SR
76 (Menon, Struijs and Whaley, 2022). Further complicating things, each item in a reporting
77 checklist implies a certain set of recommended practices that may not be explicit and might not
78 have been followed by the research team using the checklist (for example, reporting a valid
79 search may, in terms of implied guidance, require engaging with an information specialist).

80 Proficiency in the technical jargon and implied practices in systematic review requires a
81 potentially lengthy period of acculturation in relevant, competent communities of practice. Seen
82 in those terms, successful use of guidance and checklists like MECIR and PRISMA could be as
83 much an indicator of successful acculturation to a systematic review community (or specifically,
84 MECIR- or PRISMA-centric subcommunities) as they are a facilitator of writing up rigorous SR
85 manuscripts. We speculate that the experience requirement for successful compliance with
86 guidance and checklists could be lowered, if the content of guidance and checklists can be
87 reconfigured as in the following way: (1) by interpreting on behalf of a user the
88 recommendations of a conduct standard into a sequence of task-list style operational steps that
89 can be followed by a research team; and (2) by enabling the user to record what is done in each
90 operational step in such a way that the data can later be automatically used for a given reporting
91 task.

92 A recent technological innovation that could allow for this reduction in experience
93 requirement is provided by bench protocol platforms such as protocols.io (Teytelman et al.
94 2016), that facilitate “detailing, sharing, and discussing molecular and computational protocols”.
95 Bench protocol platforms have not been directly designed for automating compliance with
96 complex research guidance and reporting checklists. However, they have several features
97 including detailed recording of operational procedures, data capture when following those
98 procedures, and data export functions that allow captured data to be reused, that suggest they
99 could be appropriated for this purpose.

100 To better understand how bench protocol tools can be repurposed for complex research
101 design and documentation tasks, we set out to build a proof-of-concept general-purpose
102 operational template for planning and reporting a human environmental health SR. The template
103 is designed to have the following features:

- 104 1. Be an explicit, step-by-step sequence of operational procedures for developing and
105 documenting a human environmental health SR protocol (“operational procedure”);
- 106 2. Map how each step in the template’s operational procedure translates into compliance
107 with a selected set of conduct standards and reporting checklists (“compliance
108 mapping”);
- 109 3. Have as output structured, labelled data, to render machine-readable the operational
110 procedures and data outputs of the protocol (“data labelling”);
- 111 4. Automated assembly from the labelled data a standards- and checklist- compliant draft
112 SR protocol document (“automated documentation”).

113 We emphasise that this is a proof-of-concept project. As far as we are aware, a general-
114 purpose operational protocol has not been developed for SRs, nor has automated
115 documentation from data gathered during SR protocol development been demonstrated. As a
116 proof of concept, our technology stack is a prototype and code has not been finessed. Our
117 target audiences in this paper are tool developers seeking to support SR authors in being
118 standards-compliant, and people working in research policy who are interested in what such
119 tools might look like and how they might be expected to work. While we have endeavoured to
120 create something that could be useful in current form, the general-purpose protocol primarily
121 exists for testing and further development of ideas. We cover various aspects of the limitations
122 and development needs of our approach in the Discussion section, below.

123 **System Design**

124 *Operational procedure*

125 For the general-purpose protocol we revived an experimental build of a step-by-step
126 operationalisation of the COSTER recommendations for conducting environmental health
127 systematic reviews. The experimental build was created in the protocols.io bench protocol
128 platform (Whaley, 2020; protocols.io accessed 7 July 2022). COSTER is an adaptation for

129 human environmental health SRs of Cochrane’s MECIR standard (Whaley, Aiassa, *et al.*, 2020).
130 To build the general-purpose protocol, PW abstracted from COSTER all recommendations
131 relevant to the planning of a SR and interpreted them into a sequence of 41 explicit operational
132 steps. The operational steps include instructions on data that should be collected during each
133 step and the conditions under which each step should be marked as complete (Figure 1).

134 ***Compliance mapping***

135 PW cross-referenced each operational step against data reporting requirements for the
136 reporting checklists PRISMA-P (Moher *et al.*, 2015), PRISMA-S (Rethlefsen *et al.*, 2021),
137 ROSES for SR protocols (Haddaway *et al.*, 2018), and PROSPERO registrations (Booth *et al.*,
138 2012), to map how completion of each step contributes to fulfilling the reporting requirements of
139 several commonly-used protocol reporting checklists.

140 ***Data labelling***

141 PW created a hierarchical schema for labelling the data collected by completing each step of
142 the general-purpose protocol. The first-level data labels and cross-walk with existing SR
143 guidance and reporting checklists is shown in Table 1. The complete labelling schema is
144 available at <https://osf.io/vw4e3>.

145 The labelled data is of two types. For brief, structured data, the user inputs data into the
146 “smart component” feature of protocols.io (shown in Figure 1). For complex, unstructured data,
147 such as contextual justification for the SR, the user creates a MS Word document, gives the
148 document a specific name as per protocol instructions, and adds it to an OSF archive. (This is a
149 workaround for limits on data entry in the version of protocols.io we were using for the project.)
150 Instructions for creating an archive, naming the documents, and a link to an OSF template
151 archive with pre-named template documents are included in the general protocol.

Figure 1. Operationalisation into the general protocol of COSTER Recommendation 1.1.2: "Identify information management practices for each stage of the review, including reference and knowledge management tools, systematic review software, and statistics packages."

152 **Automated documentation**

153 The process of following all the steps of the general-purpose protocol through to completion
 154 is called in protocols.io a "run". A record of a run of our general-purpose protocols consists of
 155 the following data: the instance of the run in protocols.io itself, that can be exported as a JSON
 156 document; the data entered into the smart components, that is included in the protocols.io
 157 JSON export (the structured data); and the collection of documents uploaded to the OSF record
 158 created by the user during the run (the unstructured data). To automatically convert the run data
 159 into a draft protocol document, we created a two step-process (Figure 2).

160

Figure 2. The process for automating the documentation of a protocol run. Arrows in blue represent interfaces secured using the OAuth2 authentication standard (<https://oauth.net/2/>).

161

162 The first stage of the process is retrieval. Here, the run is retrieved from protocols.io using
 163 their API (<https://www.protocols.io/developers>). Arrows in blue in Figure 2 represent interfaces
 164 secured using the OAuth2 authentication standard (<https://oauth.net/2/>). The current build of
 165 Protocols.io (accessed 7 July 2022) returns a JSON document that consists of both data
 166 entered by the researcher, and other data including formatting instructions for online display.
 167 We therefore had to write code to extract individual fields from the protocol run via reference to
 168 structural features of the text (e.g. specific punctuation and text block positions). The fields are
 169 assigned keys in a key-value store based on the referenced standards to which they apply and
 170 the labels assigned to the step using square brackets. For example, the entry "Endnote 20" for
 171 reference manager would be stored under the key "info_manage" (label). For the entries that
 172 contain references to documents stored on the OSF archive created during the protocol run, we
 173 retrieve the OSF record using their API (<https://developer.osf.io/>). This yields a set of documents
 174 in Microsoft Word .docx format that correspond to stages mentioned in the protocol run. We
 175 export the index to JSON and store the documents separately on disk for later use. A sample of
 176 our JSON export is shown in Figure 3.

```

{
  "osf_record": "https://osf.io/zjev",
  "comp_infosci": "PW",
  "comp_eviapp": "PW, AB",
  "comp_stats": "SW, EF",
  "comp_topic": "AB, CD",
  "comp_srmeth": "PW",
  "comp_guarant": "PW",
  "info_refman": "Endnote 20",
  "info_knowman": "DistillerSR",
  "info_srsoft": "DistillerSR",
  "info_statspack": "R",
  "info_aitools": "Active Screener",

```

```

"fund_sources": "SR Funder 100",
"fund_funders": "Funded by general grant",
"fund_grantnum": "12345",
"fund_fundrole": "None",
"interests": "https://osf.io/ejcyw",
"need": "https://osf.io/vp7ak",
"q_pop_species": "Human",
"q_pop_sex": "Male",
"q_pop_age": "45-65",
"q_pop_health": "Healthy",
"q_pop_add": "None",
"q_exp_exp": "Phthalates",
"q_exp_timing": "Before birth",
"q_exp_dur": "Any",
"q_exp_dose": "Any",
"q_exp_add": "None",
"q_comp_exp": "Lower levels of phthalate exposure",
"q_comp_timing": "Before birth",
"q_comp_dur": "Any",
"q_comp_dose": "Lower",
"q_comp_add": "Exclude studies with simulataneous exposure to
pesticides",
"q_out_primary": "Gout",
"q_out_second": "Kidney disease",
[truncated]
}

```

177 **Figure 3:** A truncated sample of structured data in JSON format, as extracted from the protocol run.

178 The second stage of the automated documentation process takes these data as input and
179 reassembles them according to a template (an example template can be found at
180 <https://osf.io/nckwu>). This supports two templating languages. The first is a simple subset of
181 “mustache” markup, a widely-used templating language (<https://mustache.github.io/>). Here,
182 entries from the JSON document representing structured data from the protocols.io run can be
183 inserted into free text. For example, the entry “{{info_refman}}” is resolved to “Endnote 20”, as
184 per the example in Figure 3. The second, an unnamed proprietary template language, allows
185 template authors to include the contents of an external .docx file completely within the target
186 document, allowing them to concatenate OSF records in any order. The output of this
187 templating process is a Microsoft Word document. In our case, this is a complete summary of all
188 data from the run, intended to be edited by the reviewer into a SR protocol manuscript;
189 however, templates for summarising run data into a PRISMA report or other structured
190 document could also be created.

191 **Table 1.** Cross-walk of the top-level data labels and steps of the general-purpose protocol with items in the conduct
 192 standards and reporting checklists with which the protocol is designed to facilitate compliance. For a complete list of
 193 labels and definitions, see <https://osf.io/vw4e3>

Labels	Meaning of Labels	Step of General Protocol	Related Conduct Guideline or Reporting Checklist Items				
			COSTER	PRISMA-P	PRISMA-S	ROSES	PROSPERO (human SRs)
osf_record	Title and URL of accompanying Open Science Framework record	1	-	1a, 1b	-	1	1
competencies	Key competencies of the SR team	2	1.1.1	3b (partial)	16	-	6, 11
info_manage	Information management practices for the SR	3	1.1.2	11a	-	-	26
funding	Information about funding of the SR	4	-	5a, 5b, 5c	-	-	12
interests	Conflicts of interest management policy	5	1.1.3, 1.1.4	-	-	38	13
need	Explanation of need for the SR	6	1.2.1	6	-	5	-
rationale	The theoretical framework that supports the choice of question and use of SR methods to answer it.	7	1.2.2	6	-	5	-
question	The question being answered by the SR, characterised as a PECO statement	8	1.2.3	7, 12, 13	-	7, 8	15, 24, 25

eligibility	The eligibility criteria for evidence to be included in the SR	9	1.3	8	-	20	18-23
screening	The approach to screening evidence for eligibility for the SR	10	3.1	11b	-	18-20	26
multi_publics	The strategy for handling multiple publications from the same eligible study	11	3.4	-	-	-	-
search	The search strategy for the SR	12	1.4.1, 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.4, 2.5, 2.6	9, 10	1-6, 8, 10, 11	9, 10, 15	16, 17
rerun_search	The plans for re-running the search	13	2.7	-	12	17	16
rob	The risk of bias assessment methods for the SR	14	1.4.3, 5.3, section 5	14	-	22, 23	27
other_apppr	Other evidence appraisal methods to be used	15	7.8	-	-	22	-
char_incl	The planned characteristics of included studies table	16	1.4.2	-	-	-	-
extract_forms	The forms to be used for data extraction	17	1.4.7	12	-	-	-
synth	The methods to be used for synthesising the included evidence	18	1.4.4	15-16	-	30-34	28, 29

certainty	The methods to be used for assessing certainty in the results of the synthesis	19	1.4.5	17	-	23, 35,	-
integration	The methods to be used for integrating multiple streams of evidence	20	1.4.6	-	-	-	-
pilot_screening	Instruction to pilot the screening methods	21	1.4.7				
pilot_extraction	Instruction to pilot the data extraction forms	22	1.4.7	11c	-	25, 26	-
pilot_robot	Instruction to pilot the risk of bias assessment methods	23	1.4.7	-	-	-	-
pilot_certainty	Instruction to pilot the certainty assessment methods	24	1.4.7	-	-	-	-
write	Instruction to create a draft protocol document from the above steps	25	-	-	-	-	-
registration	Instructions and location data for registration of the protocol document	26	1.5.1	2	-	-	-
peer_review	Instructions for peer-review of the protocol document	27	1.5.2	-	14	-	-
publication	Instructions and location data for publication of the peer-reviewed	28	1.5.3	-	-	-	34

	protocol document						
Items not covered in general template		PRISMA-P	Not covered: 2, 3a, 3b, 4. 12 is covered by rationale (protocol step 7)				
		PRISMA-S	Not covered: 7, 16. 9 is covered by eligibility criteria. 13, 15 not relevant for a protocol				
		ROSES	Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 6, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 21, 27, 29, 36, 37. 16 (search validation) should be added in a future update. 19, 22, 28: COSTER recommends duplicate screening and appraisal so consistency checking is implicitly covered				
		PROSPERO	Not covered: 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 14, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40. Mainly administrative data for PROSPERO				

194

195 Anticipated results of running protocol

196 The general-purpose protocol is available at

197 <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.n92ldydzxl5b/v3>. A run of the general-purpose protocol
198 is anticipated to yield three primary outputs:

- 199 1. A comprehensive record of key data that is needed for evaluating the extent to which a
200 SR protocol is compliant with five important guidance and reporting checklists. This data
201 is generated while the user completes each step of the operationalised general protocol,
202 rather than retrospectively after a protocol development process has been completed.
- 203 2. Labelled SR protocol data that, using templates, can in principle be reassembled into
204 any protocol documentation format, e.g. a conference abstract, PROSPERO registration,
205 a protocol manuscript, a PRISMA report, a response to a data sharing request, etc.
- 206 3. After running the TARP code, a draft SR protocol manuscript. Because the draft
207 manuscript is generated by merging into a fixed template, significant editing will be
208 required before it could be considered publishable. However, since all necessary
209 information is approximately correctly located under relevant subheadings, all required
210 information is present and can be rearranged, with no information omitted.

211 An example run consisting of a PDF showing what data was input during a test run of the
212 general-purpose protocol, the processed JSON output from the test run, and an automatically

213 generated .docx template created from the test run, are available at <https://osf.io/m35px/>
214 (“Protocol publication” section). Code for the JSON conversion and .docx document generation
215 is available at <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD>.

216 Discussion

217 *Comparison to similar tools*

218 We did not do a systematic review of existing tools for this project, but we did search for
219 similar initiatives from a number of sources. PW screened all GitHub records tagged as
220 “systematic-review”, “systematic-reviews”, or “systematic-literature-reviews”, the first 10 pages
221 of results of a Google search for “automated reporting of systematic reviews”, the first 100
222 results sorted by relevance for searching “systematic review” on the protocols.io platform, the
223 protocol and reporting tools indexed in the Systematic Review Toolbox
224 (<http://systematicreviewtools.com/>), and the SR support tools reviewed by Kohl et al. (2018).
225 PW also followed up on word-of-mouth recommendations received from discussion of this
226 project with colleagues. For any tool that looked potentially similar to the present project, PW
227 checked public documentation of tool features for information about its functionality. Given the
228 limited documentation that often accompanies tools, we note that our descriptions of a tool may
229 not be a true reflection of the tool’s actual feature set.

230 The majority of GitHub records seemed to consist of document classifiers designed to
231 support the screening of search results for a SR, along with some tools to support the
232 development of search strategies. We did not find anything obviously related to facilitating
233 compliance with guidance or reporting checklists. While protocols.io has been used as a
234 repository for SR protocols, no SRs appear to have been constructed as operational procedures
235 in the platform. Methods-Wizard from the SR-Accelerator (Clark *et al.*, 2020) does have features
236 that generate methods text from input data, but it does not seem to generate labelled data that
237 is designed to be machine-readable, and it does not obviously operationalise the step-by-step
238 process of developing a SR protocol. We did note the existence of a tool for reporting trials in
239 behavioural sciences, the Paper Authoring Tool (West, 2020), that generates labelled data, has
240 features for automated drafting of a manuscript, and covers some aspects of standards
241 compliance (although without explicit cross-walking). It was not clear if the Paper Authoring Tool
242 is intended to be completed retrospectively, or is a tool that also operationalises the process of
243 planning a study in a way that facilitates compliance with conduct standards.

244 Cochrane’s RevMan software for conducting SRs of health research (Cochrane, 2020)
 245 appears to be the closest relative of our general-purpose protocol (desktop version 5.4.1,
 246 released 21 September 2020). RevMan connects components of a SR protocol or final report to
 247 the individual requirements of the MECIR standards, which in turn direct authors to detailed
 248 methodological guidance in the relevant sections of the Cochrane Handbook. However,
 249 RevMan is a reporting-focused tool that leaves implicit the step-by-step procedures one would
 250 follow as a researcher that would result in compliance with MECIR. For example, RevMan does
 251 not as an explicit step ask a research team to designate a librarian or information specialist as
 252 part of an operational process that increases the effectiveness of search strategies for a review.
 253 Also, while some aspects of reporting are automated by the simple provision in RevMan of a
 254 structured template designed around PRISMA compliance, authors still manually enter
 255 information retrospectively based on their own separate documentation of their process, rather
 256 than the SR report being directly generated from data immediately recorded during each
 257 operational step. Finally, RevMan is optimised for one SR reporting task (completing a
 258 Cochrane review) rather than designed to generate labelled data that can easily be repurposed
 259 for any SR reporting task.

260 Overall, we did not identify a tool that does all three tasks of interpreting a SR protocol into a
 261 series of operational steps linked explicitly to SR conduct standards and reporting checklists,
 262 collecting structured labelled data in completing those steps, and then automatically generating
 263 draft documentation using that data.

264 ***Potential strengths of our approach***

265 We believe our approach to a general-purpose SR protocol has three interrelated potential
 266 advantages that can be further explored and developed. These are: an emphasis on templated,
 267 algorithmic approaches to conducting and reporting research rather than heuristic approaches;
 268 taking a view of conduct standards and reporting checklists as being analogous to open-source
 269 software; and the positioning of labelled data rather than a study manuscript as the primary
 270 output of the research process. We discuss these briefly below.

271 *Algorithmic over heuristic approaches to conducting research*

272 Algorithms are a method for solving a problem in a finite number of steps via the application
 273 of a set of formally-defined processes or rules. Heuristics are practical methods for problem-
 274 solving that are derived from previous experiences with similar problems. Our opinion is that

275 systematic review is a study design that tends to be conducted heuristically, but could be made
276 more accessible to researchers if formalised to be more algorithmic. Our general-purpose
277 protocol is an attempt to do this.

278 We note that our approach is algorithmic more in the sense of a detailed recipe in a cook-
279 book than in the more formal sense of being computable. A recipe formalises a sequence of
280 inputs (ingredients) and steps that need to be followed in order to generate an output (a
281 chocolate drip cake). The purpose of the recipe is to transfer expertise between cooks without
282 them having to physically meet, one to directly train another, or a cook having to intuit the recipe
283 from the ingredients and whatever cake-making experience they may have previously acquired.
284 Successfully following the recipe still requires experience and experimentation, but the purpose
285 of the recipe is to reduce that requirement: it means cooks don't have to remember or
286 internalise a full set of complex rules, making the possibility of successfully creating the final
287 dish more accessible.

288 Algorithmic protocols could similarly help with standard and checklist compliance. In codifying
289 a set of recommended practices and the recording of data outputs from following them,
290 compliance can become a by-product of following the algorithm rather than something additional
291 that a researcher has to factor into the conduct and documentation of a study. This may help
292 address the problem of consistent under-reporting of key methodological information in SR
293 protocol registrations (Booth *et al.*, 2020) and, if extended beyond SR, also for primary studies
294 (Macleod *et al.*, 2021).

295 *Guidance and checklists as open-source software*

296 Our approach makes it more transparent how the recommendations and requirements of one
297 or more conduct guidelines, or the requirements that are implicit in one or more reporting
298 checklists, have been interpreted into an operational procedure. Unlike static documents such
299 as the PRISMA checklist (Page *et al.*, 2021), we built our procedure in a platform that emulates
300 some aspects of software development. Protocols.io implements several GitHub-like
301 collaboration features (<https://github.com/>) that allow users of the general protocol to
302 independently build on and develop our prototype. These include allowing users to post
303 questions and comments on each step of the protocol (Figure 4), and to fork protocols for
304 independent development. Forking is particularly important for tracking versions of protocols.

305 Once an operational procedure has been written up and shared, it can be discussed, tested,
 306 and finessed by those who are using it. Returning to our recipe analogy, cooks will modify
 307 recipes for working in environments where an ingredient may need to be substituted for dietary
 308 requirements, lack of availability, or for different tastes. Processes may be adapted for different
 309 circumstances or levels of skill that may make some culinary techniques unrealistic to
 310 implement. This is authoring, adapting, and versioning of the algorithm according to need.

311 Presenting the variations on a platform where relationships between versions are tracked
 312 helps make adaptations discoverable and evaluable, and allows the evolution of processes to
 313 be observed. It also implies an approach to standardisation that is more bottom-up and directly
 314 responsive to the needs of the user community than the approaches traditionally recommended
 315 for developing standards and checklists, such as the review-workshop-document process of
 316 Moher et al. (2014). We anticipate this resulting in clouds of related micro-standards adapted
 317 around the specific needs of individual research communities. While this might sound chaotic to
 318 some, forking and versioning may allow adaptations of standards to be more transparent than
 319 the often unclear ways in which users currently interpret compliance with e.g. the PRISMA
 320 checklist.

321 **Figure 4:** An example of how a user can comment on a step of the protocol to suggest a feature or improvement. A
 322 user could also generate a fork of the protocol to add steps specific to their own requirements.

323 *Labelled data as primary, manuscripts as derivative*

324 Our approach positions labelled data as the primary output of the process of conducting a
 325 research activity, with documentation as a secondary output that is derived from labelled data.
 326 This reconfigures the conventional flow of data reuse in research, whereby researchers
 327 generate data, describe the methods for acquiring and how they interpret their data in largely

328 unstructured form via a published document, from which other researchers have to abstract the
 329 data they need for reproducing or extending the original study.

330 When data, including data about methods, is labelled, compliance with a reporting checklist
 331 can become a matter of running code that generates a compliant manuscript, rather than
 332 retrospectively (and usually manually) cross-checking a document against a complex but routine
 333 set of reporting requirements. This kind of cross-checking is the sort of detailed but repetitive
 334 task that should be automated. Labelled data is also interoperable: code can be written to
 335 generate reports that are consistently compliant with one or more different reporting checklists.
 336 Availability of such code should reduce the requirement for an author of a SR protocol to be
 337 experienced in any particular reporting format in order for them to produce a comprehensive,
 338 checklist-compliant report (illustrated in Figure 5).

339
 340 **Figure 5:** Illustration of how the general-purpose protocol operationalises conduct standards into practical steps
 341 generating labelled data, which can be assembled into checklist-compliant protocol manuscripts. We believe this flow
 342 should be applicable to any study design, not just SR protocols.

343 ***Current limitations and future development***

344 *Technical issues*

345 The proof-of-concept system described above is limited by a number of technical factors in
346 our technology stack that need to be addressed via changes to the stack and/or development of
347 the components within it.

348 Firstly is the difficulty in processing Microsoft Word documents in Python. Library support for
349 templating, reading, and writing .docx files exists and is mature, but the feature set is limited.
350 We found that existing libraries were not able to apply templates reliably, nor to inspect
351 documents to separately extract text and tables in-order. This limited our templating features to
352 basic inclusion of fields within running text, or concatenation of full documents (for example,
353 documents can only be concatenated by appending them to the end of a manuscript rather than
354 inserting them in the correct place; while they are in the correct order, the user needs to cut and
355 paste to the correct location). It also makes it easy to break our code, as it looks for text features
356 which if in a different place will not be found. Updating our protocol therefore has to be done
357 with care to preserve structure, which carries implicit rules and is therefore more likely to break.

358 Secondly, it is apparent that the format used by protocols.io to deliver data over their API is
359 primarily aimed at displaying such data via a web browser, that is, the content is difficult to
360 separate from its formatting. OSF records exhibit a similar issue: though every object within the
361 OSF system has a unique ID that makes referencing simple in principle, this ID is not exposed
362 to the end user except in certain circumstances, meaning it is difficult for users to link directly to
363 documents when completing a protocol run. This could be solved a number of ways, though
364 within our system we relied on unique filenames to identify entries.

365 Thirdly, data collection features in protocols.io are not yet well-developed. The platform has
366 been designed for recording bench protocols, with data collected mainly for the purpose of
367 process auditing and validation. We appropriated these data collection features for recording
368 data from completion of a step of the general purpose protocol, but with limited success. The
369 number of .docx documents that need to be uploaded to an OSF record is an example of a
370 workaround to address this issue. Allowing users to easily create richer documentation in-situ
371 within the protocol run would be preferable to creating and linking to a series of documents
372 external to the general protocol template.

373 Mitigating these limitations requires either significant software engineering effort using
374 current technology choices, or changing to a different technology stack. Regarding the latter, we
375 suggest changing the templating format from Word to HTML, which has a much more mature
376 ecosystem of development tools, and is relatively straightforward to convert to .docx formats if
377 and when required. Other languages and platforms (such as .net) may provide better support for
378 editing such formats.

379 *General development*

380 We only did enough development of our general-purpose protocol to prove the concept.
381 Further operational steps could be added to realise a more complete mapping of conduct and
382 reporting requirements, particularly for PROSPERO where administrative data is lacking from
383 our general protocol, and for item 16 of ROSES that asks for information about validation of
384 search strategy. Nor has our operationalisation been user-tested or optimised. We also think
385 that modularisation of our protocol would be helpful for improving the efficiency of development
386 and testing, and providing opportunities for finessing specific components of the operationalised
387 process independently on an as-needed basis, as per the open software analogy discussed
388 above. For example, we have previously created a protocol for pilot-testing the screening
389 process of a SR (Whaley, Garside and Eales, 2020), that could be a module for step 21 of our
390 general-purpose protocol.

391 While our data labelling allows computational assembly of protocol documentation, our
392 tooling does not yet extend to doing anything computational with the data that has been
393 labelled. Introducing and exploiting semantic authoring features for increased machine-
394 readability and more granular labelling that is integrated with ontologies would be beneficial for
395 a number of reasons (Whaley, Edwards, *et al.*, 2020), including interoperability of data between
396 systems and the validation of entered data.

397 We also note that conduct standards and reporting checklists can be viewed as interventions
398 for improving research quality via the dissemination of written instructions. We believe we have
399 good theoretical reasons for thinking our approach could be a more effective intervention than
400 conventional standards and checklists, but there is not yet any empirical evidence that this is the
401 case. Therefore, there should be research into how effective our approach is, for whom it works
402 best, how much the granularity of operationalisation affects effectiveness, among other ideas. In
403 comparison to conventional approaches, our bottom-up approach to standardisation will have its
404 own challenges in relation to development, evaluation, and validation of the standards that are

405 produced, and the creation of suitable workflows for addressing them in what will be a nebulous
406 and distributed standards ecosystem.

407 Finally, even if the system is shown to be effective among users, there is no guarantee there
408 will be enough users of the system to make a difference to the general publishing standards
409 such systems seek to improve. We are encouraged by a recent pilot study that suggests
410 researchers may be open to increased formalisation of the reporting of study data (Wilkins *et al.*,
411 2022), and our approach is built on the assumption that automated research documentation will
412 incentivise use of operationalised protocols. However, we do not have a well-developed theory
413 based on empirical evidence as to what conditions need to be fulfilled in order for significant
414 uptake of a system such as the one we have prototyped. We subscribe to the view that
415 infrastructure should be viewed broadly as an installed base of both technology and social
416 arrangements, including group membership and conventions of practice (Edwards *et al.*, 2009),
417 and that successfully securing uptake of systems analogous to ours will require both to be
418 addressed.

419 Conclusion

420 We have presented a general-purpose SR protocol that is intended to serve as a proof-of-
421 concept for improving compliance with SR conduct standards and reporting checklists. We
422 theorised that general-purpose protocols would work by reducing the experience requirement
423 for successfully using SR standards and checklists in a research process. We articulated some
424 of the potential advantages of our approach, including viewing the problem of compliance as
425 benefiting from an algorithm-like solution, treating the development of research standards and
426 checklists as being analogous to open-source software development, and the positioning of
427 labelled data as the primary output of research from which a manuscript is a derivative product.
428 We acknowledge a range of issues with our existing technology stack, and outline a plan for
429 further development that includes technical development and the generation of empirical
430 evidence for the effectiveness of our proposed approach.

431 Supporting Information (Data, Code, and Research Materials)

Item	Link
Document templates for complex protocol data that cannot be directly entered into the general-purpose protocol	https://osf.io/h7w68/

List of labels for the protocol data	https://osf.io/vw4e3
Labelled template for generating automated protocol documentation	https://osf.io/nckwu
Draft protocol from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/zr78y
JSON database from test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/63tmz
PDF of data entered into Protocols.io on test run (test run #7)	https://osf.io/t3z98
Full set of documents created for test run and uploaded to OSF as per general-purpose protocol instructions (test run #7)	https://osf.io/m35px/
Code for JSON conversion from Protocols.io protocol run and document generation	https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD

432

433 **Metadata**

434 **Funding**

435 Lancaster University Impact Acceleration Award: “TARPD Prototype Tool for Automated
436 Research Project Documentation”

437 **Preregistration**

438 This study was not preregistered.

439 **Declaration of Interests**

440 PW declares the following financial interests: consultancy services for the Evidence-Based
441 Toxicology Collaboration (EBTC) at Johns Hopkins University Bloomberg School of Public
442 Health; Lancaster University, mainly around securing impact of his PhD research (completed
443 2020); the University of Central Lancashire (UCLAN), which has involved developing furniture
444 fire safety models relevant to reducing the impact of the use of chemical flame retardants in
445 ensuring fire safety for the UK Government Agency OPSS; and for Yordas Group, to deliver
446 training in SR methods for EU JRC. PW also receives an Honorarium as Systematic Reviews
447 Editor for the journal Environment International. In general, PW’s consultancy work is around
448 development and promotion of systematic review methods in environmental health research,
449 delivering training around these methods, and providing editorial services. He is applying for
450 funding to develop evidence surveillance and automated SR documentation methods through
451 Lancaster University, which if successful will arrive within the next two years.

452 PW also declares the following non-financial interests: a historical, public commitment to high
453 quality systematic review methods in support of environmental health policy and decision-
454 making; active involvement in a range of projects intended to improve research standards in
455 evidence synthesis. These include development of SR conduct standards (e.g. COSTER),
456 reporting checklists (e.g. ROSES), and critical appraisal tools (e.g. CREST_Triage, IV-CAT) to
457 support the production of high quality systematic reviews, evidence maps, and other study
458 designs. PW is an active member of the GRADE Working Group, has a senior role at EBTC that
459 involves promoting SR and other evidence-based methods in toxicology and environmental
460 health, and is a member of an informal UK NGO network promoting good environmental policy
461 in the UK, and several Brussels-based environmental policy advocacy groups including HEAL

462 and EEB. In general, PW has a strong interest in supporting precautionary, evidence-based
463 approaches to environmental health policy.

464 SW declares providing scientific & technical consultancy services as a subcontractor to PW
465 on a UK OPSS-funded study into the use of chemical fire retardants in furniture. SW has also
466 provided scientific consultancy services in unrelated fields, and states that publication of work in
467 any area impacts chances of future employment.

468 AMS declares that, as part of her role at Bond University, she provides training in: evidence-
469 based medicine and systematic review methodology (including automation tools), to Australia-
470 based academics, clinicians and students. Those workshops charge a registration fee. AMS is
471 part of the Systematic Review Accelerator team at Bond University, which develops and makes
472 publicly available automation tools to accelerate completion of systematic reviews, as well as
473 conducting research in this area (all tools are available free of charge). AMS is an Associate
474 Editor for Systematic Reviews, a BMC / Springer Nature journal (non-remunerated).

475 JV is a Senior Research Associate at Lancaster University and declares having no interests
476 that may compromise the integrity of the research described in this manuscript.

477 **Ethics Declarations**

478 Ethical approval and informed consent were not required for this research, as it involved neither
479 human nor animal participants.

480 **Data availability**

481 All data is available from the accompanying OSF project record at
482 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZJEVP> and GitHub repository at
483 <https://github.com/StephenWattam/TARPD>

484 **Authors' Contributions**

485 *Created using Tenzing app (Holcombe et al., 2020).*

486 Conceptualization: Paul Whaley. Data curation: Stephen Wattam. Funding acquisition: Paul
487 Whaley and John Vidler. Investigation: Paul Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Methodology: Paul
488 Whaley and Stephen Wattam. Project administration: John Vidler. Software: Stephen Wattam.
489 Supervision: John Vidler. Validation: Stephen Wattam. Visualisation: Paul Whaley and Stephen

490 Wattam. Writing - original draft: Paul Whaley. Writing - review & editing: Paul Whaley, Stephen
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